

ASSESSMENT OF THE TYPE OF STATISTICAL DISTRIBUTION CONCERNING STRENGTH PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials show a degradation of properties depending on service life. This creates the necessity to find tailored methods to determine strength and residual strength of composite cylinders. The determination can be done e.g. by load cycles tests. The result needs a statistical assessment for the precise description of strength. Especially the statistical assessment of load cycle strength properties has a high uncertainty. It is unclear if a Log-Normal distribution, a WEIBULL distribution or others, describe the scatter behaviour of residual strength properties correctly.

Distribution functions aim at approximating the frequency of occurrence of residual load cycle strength for high survival rates. An assumption has to be found and confirmed to prevent over-estimation of reliability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Current codes and standards define fix approval criterions to ensure sufficient load cycle strength of composite cylinders. For example ISO 11119-2 demands demonstration of hydraulic load cycle testing of 2 test specimens up to 12,000 load cycles without leakage to permit an approval for an unlimited life-time. If pressure receptacles need to be approved for limited life, ISO 11119-2 has lower demands on load cycle resistance. 500 load cycles per annum of design life have to be achieved for approval. If “leak-before-burst” properties can be demonstrated, an even lower amount of 250 load cycles is sufficient.

These approval criteria are mainly based on experience with cylinders made from metallic materials. A basic assumption is that one filling cycle in service roughly complies with one hydraulic load cycle during a load cycle test. As shown in [1] this assumption cannot be transferred to composite cylinders. Especially at the beginning of life the loss of hydraulic load cycle can be up to 250 times more than the real number of filling cycles.

Additionally a test of just two specimens and the current praxis to stop a load cycle test after reaching the approval criterion do not ensure that all cylinders from same design type fulfill this criterion as well. Such tests provide no information about mean value and scatter of actually existing load cycle strength.

A probabilistic approach from BAM for a statistical assessment of load cycle test results [2, 3, 4, 5] bases on a extended load cycle test of at least 5 specimens until leakage or up to 50,000 load cycles without leakage. For most type II & III composite cylinders (metallic liner material) such tests allow to determine mean value and scatter of load cycle strength. The safety criterion is in this case a minimum required survival rate (SR_{min}) for end of life. SR_{min} is in between of $SR_{min} \geq 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ (99.99%) up to $1 \cdot 10^{-8}$ (99.999999%) and depends on resulting consequence of leakage according to type of gas, volume and maximum service pressure of the tested composite cylinder [1].

A statistical assessment of load cycle tests and resulting survival rates for composite cylinders allow the use of untapped reserves in material and design as well the recognition of unsafe design types with high scatter.

2 EXTRAPOLATION OF SURVIVAL RATES

Unfortunately, the statistical assessment of load cycle tests has a basic problem. The desired SR_{min} cannot be proven with experiments due to small sample sizes. The reason is found in the aspired small likeliness of a failure event. It could only be proven by numerous reruns of the experiment. The direct experimental proof of a SR_{min} of 99% would require more than 50 test specimens. Proving $SR_{min} = 99.9\%$ would already require more than 300 test specimens.

The determination of such a high survival rate from a sample size of 5 to 10 single values requires an extrapolation by statistical distribution functions. Aim of a statistical distribution function is to describe the frequency of occurrence for a defined property, in the mentioned case load cycle strength. The parameters of a distribution function need to be estimated from the tested sample. The resulting distribution functions allows to extrapolate the survival rate for a given load cycle strength or the other way around to extrapolate a load cycle strength for a given survival rate.

Figure 1: Extrapolation of survival rates from limited sample size

The basic concept of extrapolation of survival rates by an assumed distribution function is shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 1 shows a Gaussian probability net with a sample of 9 single load cycle test results. The results are sorted in ascending order and every value is assigned to a survival rate by a specific ranking function. Survival rates in an area between approximately 5% and 95% can be directly proven by

measured values. Higher and lower survival rates need to be extrapolated by an assumed distribution function or can be estimated by numeric simulation like a Monte-Carlo-Simulation.

The marked red area presents the amount of cylinders who already failed due to fatigue loads.

3 DISTRIBUTION FUNCTIONS FOR RESIDUAL LOAD CYCLES

Fig. 1 shows that the real survival rate in the required area is actually unknown. Therefore an assessment based on survival rates strongly depends on the course of the assumed distribution function.

Statistic tools provide a large variety of different types of distribution functions. For many technical applications, the assumption of a symmetric normal distribution is the best choice. However, particular load cycling tests are in general asymmetric distributed. Therefore the preferred distribution function should be a Log-Normal or Weibull distribution.

Basic assumption of a Log-Normal distribution is that the logarithmic values of a property are distributed according to a Normal distribution. This leads to a distribution with a minimum value of zero and a positive skew. A positive skew means an asymmetric distribution where low values occur with a higher probability than high values.

Parameters of a Log-Normal distribution are logarithmic mean value and logarithmic standard deviation. These parameters can be estimated from a sample as shown in Eq. 1 and 2. Survival rate SR and load cycle strength N can be calculated according to Eq. 3.

$$m_{log} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \log_{10} N_i \quad (1)$$

$$s_{log} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (\log_{10}(N_i) - m_{log})^2} \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi^{-1}(1 - SR(N)) = \frac{\log_{10}(N) - m_{log}}{s_{log}} \quad (3)$$

A Weibull distribution is asymmetric as well but can be adjusted to different applications in a much better way than a Log-Normal distribution. A Weibull distribution requires three parameters as shown in Eq. 4, characteristic lifetime T, shape parameter b and failure free time T₀. The shape parameter b allows creating a distribution function with varying scatter and positive or negative skew. The failure free time T₀ represents the minimum value of the distribution function. The definition of a positive failure free time creates an area where the survival rate for the whole population is 100%, so below T₀ no failure can occur.

$$SR(N) = e^{-\left(\frac{N - T_0}{T - T_0}\right)^b} \quad (4)$$

The result from an extrapolation by a distribution function strongly depends on the assumed type of distribution function and its estimated parameters. Fig. 2 shows a Gaussian probability net with the extrapolated load cycle strength for SR = 99.99% based on different assumed distribution function for the same sample results.

Figure 2: Comparison of assumed distribution functions for same test results

A Normal distribution in a Gaussian probability net is always a straight line. In the presented case (Fig. 2) the Normal distribution crosses $N = 0$ at around 99.95 %. The result for $SR = 99.99\%$ is already a negative number of load cycles. The cross point with $N = 0$ and the negative number of load cycles can be interpreted as following. If the measured load cycle strength would really follow a Normal distribution then 5 of 10,000 cylinders are already damaged by leakage.

As already mentioned, according to the state of science and research a Normal distribution is not recommend to describe load cycle test results. The reason is that the assumed symmetry around the arithmetic mean value does not exist for load cycle test results.

Both Weibull distributions in Fig. 2 with $T_0 = 0$ and $T_0 = 8000$ converge in each case to the corresponding T_0 . Therefore the extrapolation of load cycle strength for $SR = 99.99\%$ also results in a positive number of load cycles. The result of a Weibull distribution strongly depends on the assumed T_0 .

A Log-Normal distribution always converges to zero. The extrapolation for $SR = 99.99\%$ results into a similar number of load cycles like a Weibull distribution with $T_0 = 8000$. A Log-Normal distribution is in some cases a good approximation of Weibull distribution with a high positive failure free time. In the area of SR between $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ up to $1 \cdot 10^{-8}$ a Weibull distribution with $T_0 = 0$ is a more conservative approach then a Log-Normal distribution.

In principle there are a lot of statistic tests (goodness of fit test) to check the significance of an assumed distribution function for a specific sample [6]. But usually these tests are not able to deliver a sufficient result based on a small sample size. Because in the area that can be proven by real test results all shown distribution functions are nearly congruent, as shown in Fig. 2. Therefore it is actually not possible to check the individual type of distribution function with a statistical test for small samples. The statistical assessment of small samples requires the definition of a general assumption for the type of distribution function. This leads to the main question, which type of distribution function would be the most suitable choice for a safety assessment of load cycle results from composite cylinders?

4 DISTRIBUTION OF RESIDUAL LOAD CYCLE OF AGED BREATHING AIR CYLINDERS

A statement about the distribution function of the load cycle strength of Composite cylinders requires studies of samples with a much larger sample size than usually available. The discussion about the type of distribution function already started in [7] on an example of type III breathing air cylinders. The 25 tested composite cylinders were decommissioned after 15 years in service by the Berlin fire department. Due to the extreme operating conditions the sample is a mix of cylinders with a wide range of different load histories.

The 25 test results include 4 early failures with comparatively high scatter and low numbers of residual load cycles. The early failures seem to represent a share of highly loaded cylinders with a significantly reduced residual life. This is probably a result of partly extreme operating conditions during service and training at the fire department. Therefore a statistical description of the whole sample is quite difficult.

Fig. 3 shows a comparison between two Weibull distribution functions. The red line describes the whole sample, including early failures by a Weibull distribution with a negative failure free time of $T_0 = -4000$. The cross point between the assumed distribution function and end of life $N = 1$ results into a survival rate for end of life of around $SR_{EoL} = 99.9\%$. This means, based on the assumed distribution function, approximately 1 of 1,000 cylinders is already damaged by a leakage at the date of decommissioning.

The blue area represents possible distribution functions of the sample without early failures. The estimated failure free time T_0 is between 3,000 and 7,000 load cycles. In case that the focus is set on this part of the sample, there would still remain a comfortable reserve of residual life time.

Figure 3: Estimation of failure free time for breathing air cylinders after 15 years in service

As shown in Fig. 3 an assessment of load cycle numbers from a large sample allows to estimate a failure free time. On the one hand a negative failure free time could possibly occur in case of very high intensity of use and after long time in service. On the other hand a group of cylinders with less intensity of use can also show a positive failure free time.

5 AGING OF COMPOSITE CYLINDER

The assumption of a failure-free time for a type III composite cylinder under new or slightly used condition, results from the typical behavior of the metallic liner material under dynamic loads. The initiation of a crack and its growth over the entire material thickness requires a certain number of load cycles until a leakage occurs.

Fig. 4 shows a schematic concept of Weibull distributions for the residual load cycle strength of composite cylinders over their lifetime. The failure free time T_0 possesses its maximum value at beginning of life. An increase of service life leads to a left shift of the distribution function. This results from the assumed reduction of failure free time over lifetime. The end of life (EoL) is reached at $T_0 = 0$. Further use of the composite cylinder exceeds the safe lifetime. The survival rate for $N = 0$ decreases and the probability of failure increases accordingly.

Figure 4: Assumed changes in a Weibull distribution of residual load cycle strength over life time

The main problem of this concept is that the required effort to determine a failure-free time and its change over lifetime is not economically feasible. Such tests require a high number of specimens and the results are still quite uncertain. Therefore a failure free time for a statistical assessment of new or aged populations of composite cylinders is for practical purpose not available.

For a general distribution function of load cycle strength two alternatives are available. A Log-Normal distribution is a sufficient approximation of a Weibull distribution with a high positive but unknown failure free time. For this reason a Log-Normal distribution can be used to describe populations of composite cylinders in new or slightly aged conditions.

Otherwise a Log-Normal distribution is not suitable to estimate a survival rate of aged cylinders which are close to or exceed their end of life. These populations of composite cylinders can be described by a Weibull distribution with a failure free time of $T_0 = 0$. This simplifies the Weibull distribution to a function with only two parameters, as shown in Eq. 5.

$$SR(N) = e^{-\left(\frac{N}{T}\right)^b} \quad (5)$$

A Weibull distribution with two parameters underestimates the residual load cycle strength of composite cylinders in new and slightly aged conditions. But with the proceeding aging of a

population the shape of the distribution will align to end of life $T_0 = 0$ as well. Therefore the general assumption of a Weibull distribution with $T_0 = 0$ ensures a conservative estimation of survival rate for end of life.

In case of exceeding the safe service life, as shown in Fig. 3 for breathing air cylinders, a Weibull distribution with $T_0 = 0$ is not a conservative assumption. However, this case is represented by a very low median of residual load cycle strength and a high scatter value. So also a Weibull distribution with $T_0 = 0$ would lead to the conclusion that the end of safe service life is already reached. Only the estimation of the amount of failed cylinders is not possible with this assumption.

Overall, a Weibull distribution with a failure free time of $T_0 = 0$ seems to be a suitable and conservative assumption for a safety assessment. The implementation of the assumed distribution function in a method for safety assessment of load cycle test results is illustrated in the following.

6 ASSUMED DISTRIBUTION FUNCTION FOR STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT

As discussed in [1] the aging process of a population of composite cylinders is represented by a reduction of mean residual load cycle strength and an increase of scatter during service life. Fig. 5 summarizes the results from load cycle tests of composite cylinders after different stages of service life. The grouping of test results into samples with similar ageing conditions allow to estimate the development of median (SR = 50%) and scatter which are based on an assumed Weibull distribution. The change in scatter is indicated by the distance between SR = 10 % and SR = 90 %.

Figure 5: Scatter and median of residual load cycle strength over service life

The line of SR = 50 % shows a reduction of mean residual load cycle strength over service life. The increasing scatter is illustrated by the increasing distance between the lines for SR = 10 % and SR = 90 %. The actual survival rate for end of life is not shown in Fig. 5.

The visualization of a survival rate at EoL (SR_{EoL}) for a single sample or a group of samples with different aging conditions can be done by a performance chart as presented in [1]. The performance chart allows a fast and easy estimation and comparison of survival rates for samples of load cycle test results. A whole sample within the performance chart (Fig. 6) is represented as one dot by median $N_{50\%}$ and scatter N_s . Median and scatter need to be calculated based on the parameters of a Log-Normal distribution according to Eq. 6 and 7.

$$N_{50\%} = 10^{m_{log}} \quad (6)$$

$$N_s = 10^{s_{log}} \quad (7)$$

The performance chart contains lines of constant survival rate (iso-asfalia). A sample above e.g. the line for $SR = 1 - 10^{-6} = 99.9999\%$ fulfills the requirement for $SR_{min} \geq 99.9999\%$ for end of life with a confidence level of 95%. A confidence level considers general uncertainties which results from a limited sample size. In fact a sample has not exactly the same properties as the whole population. Therefore a confidence level of 95% means that the real survival rate of the whole population of cylinders is with a probability of 5% in the worst case lower than calculated.

Fig. 6 combines the reduction of median and the increase of scatter during service life and shows the resulting survival rate for the tested type of composite cylinders. Even after 13 years of service life the tested population of cylinders is still on a safe side. A statement about further development of sample properties or safe service life is possible in general, but it contains a high degree of uncertainty.

Figure 6: Survival rate of samples from composite cylinders over service life

The shown iso-asfalia for SR_{EOL} in Fig. 6 already include the assumption of a Weibull distribution with $T_0 = 0$. This is realized by a transformation of the parameters from a Log-Normal distribution into a Weibull distribution according to [8]. This transformation is based on two reference points ($SR = 16\%$; $SR = 84\%$) as shown in Fig. 7. The parameters of the resulting Weibull distribution can be calculated according to Eq. 8 and 9.

$$T = N_{50\%} \cdot N_s^{0.48416} \quad (8)$$

$$b = 1.02743 / (2 \cdot \log(N_s)) \quad (9)$$

This procedure allows to use the performance chart with the parameters of a Log-Normal distribution, which are quite easily to calculate. But the actual assessment by the iso-asfalia for SR_{EOL} is based on survival rates which are precalculated by a Weibull distribution.

Figure 7: Transformation of a Log-Normal into a Weibull distribution

The resulting distribution functions for the samples, as presented in Fig. 5 and 6, are shown in Fig. 8. Potentially existing failure-free times are not considered. Due to this the survival rate may probably be underestimated, especially for the sample after approximately 1 year in service.

Figure 8: Assumed Weibull distributions of residual load cycle strength over service life

The statistical assessment of the samples from Design A in Fig.5, 6 and 8 shows a high survival rate for end of life over the whole analysed service life. However, as shown in Fig. 8, the minimum requirement for unlimited service life (12,000 load cycles) could only be met by around 99.9% of all cylinders after 1 year in service. This value decreases to approximately 97% to 98% after 7 to 13 years in service. So also with a median of more than 20,000 load cycle at beginning of service life there is a risk that 1 of 1,000 cylinders would not fulfill the minimum requirement for unlimited service life.

The tested population of composite cylinders probably still possesses a positive failure free time after 13 years in service. But this failure free time can not be estimated and considered due to the limited sample size.

A Weibull distribution with $T_0 = 0$ as a general distribution function for load cycle tests of composite cylinders is a suitable and conservative assumption for a safety assessment in relation to the end of safe service life. It needs to be considered that this assumption will always lead to a survival rate below 100%. So the result is in any case a positive failure rate ($FR = 1 - SR$), even for brand new populations of composite cylinders. As discussed this results from the unknown failure free time. Therefore the extrapolation of an extremely low failure rate of $FR \leq 10^{-8}$ can be treated as out of the model boundaries and is not relevant for practical purpose.

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A statement about very rare failure events based on a small samples size requires the extrapolation of survival rates $SR \geq 99.99\%$ by distribution functions. This approach is based on general assumptions and therefore it contains a high degree of uncertainty. Especially the selected type of distribution function and its estimated parameters have a major influence on the result of a safety assessment. As shown, a decision about an individual distribution function for a small sample is not possible.

Suitable distribution functions to describe load cycle test results are in general a Log-Normal and a Weibull distribution. A Weibull distribution requires in particular a definition of a failure time T_0 as minimum value. The minimum value of a Log-Normal distribution is always zero but as shown, this distribution function delivers in the required area for safety assessment, between of $SR \geq 99.99\%$ and $SR \leq 99.999999\%$, similar results as a Weibull distribution with a high positive minimum value.

The statistical assessment of large samples ($n = 25$) of type III composite cylinders after 15 years in service show, that positive and negative failure free times may occur. A reduction of failure free time over lifetime depending on intensity of use can be assumed.

However, the small usual sample size of $5 \leq n \leq 15$ for an assessment of composite cylinders is to less for a determination of an individual failure free time of each sample. Therefore the distribution function needs to be approximated without knowing a failure free time. In case of cylinders in new conditions a Log-Normal distribution is a suitable choice to describe the residual load cycle strength. But as shown, a Log-Normal distribution is not suitable to estimate a survival rate of aged cylinders which are close to or exceed their end of safe service life. In this case a Weibull distribution with $T_0 = 0$ as a general distribution function for load cycle tests of composite cylinders is a suitable and conservative assumption for safety assessments.

Based on this assumption, the survival rate of a population of composite cylinders can be estimated and compared with the presented performance chart. A prediction of safe service life is possible in general, but contains a high degree of uncertainty.

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